

Effect of Sub-monolayer Adsorption on Rheological Characteristics and Dynamic Behaviour of Fluid Interfaces: Experimental Evidence for the Guggenheim's Model of Extended Interface

Afshin Asadzadeh Shahir^a, Dimi Arabadzhieva^b, Anh V Nguyen^{a,*}, Hrisi Petkova^b, Stoyan I Karakashev^c, Elena Mileva^b

^a School of Chemical engineering, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, QLD 4072, Australia

^b Institute of Physical Chemistry, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Block 11, Sofia 1113, Bulgaria

^c Department of Physical Chemistry, Sofia University, 1 James Bourchier av., Sofia 1164, Bulgaria

Abstract

The surface saturation of solutions of three low-molecular-weight surface-active alcohols were identified independently using sum frequency generation spectroscopy. Tensiometry showed that solution surface tension kept decreasing uniformly and considerably even after full saturation of the adsorption monolayer. We employed Guggenheim's model of extended interface to attribute this observation to the ongoing adsorption of alcohol molecules beneath the saturated topmost adsorption layer. Our investigation of the dynamic behaviour of thin liquid films of alcohol solutions revealed the tremendous effect of sub-monolayer adsorption on the rheological characteristics of surface. Sub-monolayer region was found to function as a supplementary source of alcohol molecules. The fast diffusion of surfactants from sub-monolayer to the topmost adsorption layer imposed a buffering effect on the dynamic response of the surface through diminishing the surface tension gradient created by surface expansion. This resulted in sudden drop of the Gibbs elasticity and consequently faster decaying foam.

Keywords: *Sum Frequency Generation Spectroscopy, Thin liquid Film, Gibbs Dividing Surface Plane, Guggenheim's Model of Extended Interface, Surfactant, Sub-monolayer adsorption*

1. Introduction

A detailed understanding of physico-chemical properties of fluid-liquid interfaces is of critical importance to many industrial processes. To achieve this, a reliable model of interface that provides a basis for thermodynamic description of interfacial phenomena should exist. Such a model was first developed by *J. Willard Gibbs* in 1870s.¹ In Gibbs convention, the interface between two bulk phases is modelled as an ideally sharp plane, namely *Gibbs dividing plane*. The difference between the concentrations of a component, *i*, at unit area of the dividing plane and its bulk concentration (c_i) is then defined as its surface excess (Γ_i). The dividing plane is conventionally positioned so that the surface excess of solvent becomes zero. The relative adsorption of the component *i* with respect to the solvent is then given by the famous Gibbs adsorption isotherm (GAI):^{2, 3}

$$\Gamma_i = -\frac{1}{nRT} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d \ln a_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of species formed by dissociation of adsorbate within the solution. R and T are the gas constant and temperature of the solution, respectively. σ is the solution surface tension and a_i is the bulk activity of component *i* which can be replaced by bulk concentration c_i in sufficiently dilute solutions. Moreover, the Gibbs surface excess can be defined by the following relation¹:

$$\Gamma_i = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [a_i(z) - a_i^{ideal}] dz \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) shows that the Gibbs surface excess is related to the concentration profile of component *i* underneath and above the Gibbs dividing plane. Hence, every form of sub-

monolayer adsorption is accounted for by Eq. (1). Furthermore, the combination of Eqs. (1) and (1) indicates that both the sub-monolayer and monolayer surfactant adsorptions contribute to the value of the surface tension of surfactant solution. The major confusion in the literature on adsorption is based on the assumption that the Gibbs surface excess is equivalent only to the adsorption monolayer. This assumption finds its historical roots in the “adsorption lattice theory”, which has been derived for gas adsorption on solid surfaces^{4, 5} and applied furthermore to surfactant adsorption on gas/liquid surfaces⁴⁻⁶.

For this reason when applying the GAI to describe surfactant adsorption, majority of the community have unsuspectingly supposed that the surfactant molecules adsorb at the interface in the form of a monolayer which is virtually equivalent to the Gibbs dividing plane. With this viewpoint, the adsorption monolayer should therefore be, according to Eq. (1), the only contributor to the solution surface tension and since Gibbs dividing plane has a limited capacity to accommodate surfactant molecules, the surface tension would inevitably stop decreasing at some bulk surfactant concentration. This point is referred to as the critical micellization concentration (CMC) at which the surface is believed to be nearly saturated and formation of micelles within the bulk hinders further adsorption of surfactants.³ As a result, solution surface tension levels off. Nevertheless, the assumption of full surface saturation at CMC has recently been argued by the community.⁷⁻¹²

The monolayer adsorption has also been the basic assumption behind many other adsorption isotherms vastly used by the scientists to analyse the surface tension data for thousands of surfactant systems. Among the most popular ones are the isotherms of Langmuir,¹³ Frumkin¹⁴ and Volmer.¹⁵ This view is still dominating the community and has well proved correct for many surfactant systems. This can be explained with the criterion for the validity of this assumption – the relation between the surface tension and the surfactant bulk concentration. This relation produces dependence of the surfactant adsorption on the gas/liquid interface on the surfactant bulk concentration, which often cannot be checked experimentally. The well accepted assumption that the surfactant forms adsorption monolayer on air/water interface until CMC cannot explain the maximum in the foam stability at certain optimal concentration C_{opt} of surfactants with small molecular weight¹⁶⁻¹⁸. This optimal concentration C_{opt} is usually a little bit smaller than the CMC value ($C_{opt} < CMC$). Hence, according to the above mentioned assumption the adsorption of the surfactant Γ at the optimal concentration C_{opt} has not yet reached its maximal value Γ_{∞} ($\Gamma < \Gamma_{\infty}$) The further increase of the concentration of the surfactant should make the adsorption layer denser, thus

approaching Γ_∞ value, corresponding to more stable foams. On the contrary, at $C > C_{opt}$ the foam becomes more unstable instead of more stable. According to Adam¹⁹ the surfactant concentrations, which are a little bit smaller than the CMC value belongs to the last part of the surface tension isotherm at which $d\sigma/dc \approx 0$, while the maximum foam stability should correspond to the maximal value of $d\sigma/dc$. For this reason Adam assumed that the maximum foam stability at $C_{opt} < CMC$ can be explained with some lack of precision of the very experiment. However, such an assumption is obviously incorrect. To explain the above mentioned experimental facts, one should consider the Gibbs elasticity. The Gibbs elasticity of foam film can be defined by^{20, 21}:

$$E_g = 2 \frac{d\sigma}{dS} S \quad (1),$$

where σ is the surface tension of the film surfaces, and S is the surface of the film. It quantifies the film's ability to oppose the sudden expansion or shrinking of the foam lamellae. Moreover, the value of E_g depends on both the rate of deformation of the lamellae and the thickness of the latter. The foam lamella (foam film) is assumed with constant volume. Hence, its expansion makes the film thinner while its shrinking makes the film thicker. The deformation is usually done on small area of the foam lamellae. At infinitely fast expansion, when the equilibrium between the film surfaces of the deformed area and the bulk of the film cannot be established, E_g acquires maximal value. In such a case the increase of the value of σ is due to the decrease of the surfactant surface concentration, which has not been compensated by the influx of new quantities of the surfactant molecules from the bulk of the film. At slower expansion, (this corresponds to a broad area of rates of deformation) the surfactant surface concentration of the expanded area decrease due to the general redistribution of the surfactant molecules from the deformed part of the film. When the thickness of the expanded part of foam lamella becomes smaller, part of the surfactant molecules in the bulk of the same spot is shifted towards the neighbouring (non-deformed) vicinity of the foam lamellae. This causes certain depletion of surfactant molecules in bulk of the deformed part of the foam lamellae, resulting in weaker influx compensation with surfactant molecules on the expanded spot from the foam lamellae. Therefore, the cases of ultrafast and slower expansion of the foam lamellae become practically identical. If the expansion of a certain area from the foam lamellae is conducted very slowly the neighbouring (non-deformed) vicinity of the foam lamellae (bulk + surface) participates into the general

redistribution of the surfactant molecules. This results in a smaller increase in the value of σ in the expanded area of the foam lamellae. In the limit case of infinitely slow expansion of a certain spot from the foam lamellae a full compensation with surfactant molecules from the non-deformed vicinity of the foam lamellae occurs. Hence, the value of the surface tension σ in the expanded area will not increase, and the Gibbs elasticity under such conditions will vanish. Equation (1) can be transformed²¹ in the following relation:

$$E_g = \frac{4RT\Gamma_\infty^2 c}{h(c+B)^2 + 2\Gamma_\infty B} \quad (1)$$

where Γ_∞ is the maximal surfactant adsorption on air/water interface, c is its concentration into the bulk of the foam lamellae, B is a constant, which is reversed to the equilibrium adsorption constant ($B=1/K$), and h is thickness of the foam lamellae. Equation (1) is valid for single foam lamellae (foam film). The surfactant in the bulk of the foam lamellae at every thickness is depleted compared to the surfactant in the bulk of the surfactant aqueous solution^{22, 23}. Hence, the surfactant located among the bubbles of the foam is depleted as well. Moreover, foams, which are stabilized by surfactants with low molecular weight, (e.g. MIBC, pentanol, *etc.*), are transient and wet foams with distance between the bubbles in order of 10 μm and more. It was established that the value of the Gibbs elasticity of the foam films has maximum at a certain optimal surfactant concentration c_{opt} into the bulk of the foam lamellae^{20, 21}.

$$c_{opt} = B\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\Gamma_\infty}{Bh}} \quad (1)$$

As far as for the low homologues of the fatty acids and alcohols is valid the Szyszkowski equation, at high thickness of order of 1 mm of the foam lamellae (e.g. transient foams) the second additive of Eq. (1) can be neglected. Yet, we will assume that in our case we have an average thickness of the foam lamella valued at 10 μm . An interesting point here is the ratio between the optimal concentrations into the bulk of the foam lamellae and into the bulk of the aqueous surfactant solution, which is the level of surfactant depletion into the foam lamella.

The last two decades witnessed the report of interfacial multi-layering for some surface active molecules, detected by experimental tools such as neutron and x-ray reflectivity.²⁴ *Wantke et al.* have already discussed the possibility of sublayer adsorption and its contribution to the solution surface tension and the dynamic behaviour of adsorption layer.^{25, 26} Accordingly, our previous work also revealed that the surface tension of a low

molecular weight foaming alcohol solution kept decreasing considerably even after the full surface monolayer saturation which was detected independently using sum frequency generation (SFG) spectroscopy.²⁷ Meanwhile, Guggenheim has already provided an alternative definition of interface which accounts for a so-called “*surface layer*” with a certain volume (thickness, d^σ) rather than a diving plane.²⁸ *Wantke et al.* thermodynamically explained that such a definition would allow for consideration of additional adsorption sites beneath the topmost monolayer whose compositions could effectively contribute to the measured solution surface tension:²⁵

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_m + \frac{n_{sub-m}}{S} \quad (2)$$

Γ is the total surfactant excess adsorbed at the surface layer of thickness d^σ . n_{sub-m} is the real number of the adsorbed surfactant molecules at sub-monolayer region. S is area of the surface layer and Γ_m is the surface excess at adsorption monolayer which can still be given by the GAI:²⁵

$$\Gamma_m \cong -\frac{1}{RT} \frac{d\sigma}{d \ln a} \quad (3)$$

Despite the different geometric definitions of the interface, the thermodynamic foundations of both Gibbs and Guggenheim conventions are the same. We will show that these two models of interface are not distinguishable by simply measuring the equilibrium thermodynamic properties of interface such as surface tension. Nonetheless, the existence of a sub-monolayer is expected to alter the dynamic behaviour of interfaces, e.g. its rheological characteristics. A topic that has not been properly addressed by the community yet. The oscillating bubble/drop methods have undoubtedly been among the most useful and popular techniques to extract macro-level information about the interfacial dynamic parameters such as dynamic surface tension,²⁹ dilatational viscoelastic modulus³⁰ and kinetic parameters of surfactant adsorption.^{31, 32} Besides, thin liquid films (TLFs) has well proved suitable model systems to study the static and dynamic behaviour of adsorption monolayers at fluid interfaces. Because of the dynamic nature of TLFs during drainage, oscillating bubble/drop technique has effectively been combined with TLF drainage measurements, e.g. micro-interferometry and macroscopic foamability, in order to investigate the effect of surface rheology on the stability of foams and emulsions.³³⁻³⁶

In the present work, we have discussed the possibility of sub-monolayer adsorption for three low molecular weight alcohols; *n*-pentanol, methyl isobutyl carbinol (MIBC) and *n*-hexanol (Fig. 1). Also, its influence on the rheological characteristics of air-water interface has been studied using a combination of dilatational elasticity, foamability measurements and micro-interferometry of TLF drainage. As shown in a previous paper,²⁷ the surface tension plots of these alcohols, unlike conventional long-chain surfactants, lack a distinguishable CMC point that makes it impossible to identify the monolayer saturation concentration (C_{MS}). Therefore, the surface coverage should be tracked directly and independently of the bulk. Thankfully, this has been made possible by inherently surface-specific non-linear spectroscopy techniques, e.g. sum frequency generation (SFG)³⁷ and second harmonic generation (SHG).^{38, 39} Combining spectroscopy results with static surface tension data, we have discussed that sub-monolayer adoption is justifiable under Guggenheim convention. The rheological characteristics of thin liquid films stabilised by these three alcohols further confirmed the existence of the proposed sub-monolayer region to which the community has not paid appropriate attention yet.

Figure 1. The molecular structure of the studied alcohols.

2. Theoretical aspects

2.1. Sum frequency generation (SFG) spectroscopy

The theoretical and experimental aspects of SFG spectroscopy have already been presented elsewhere.⁴⁰ A summary is provided here to clarify the justifiability of our conclusions. SFG is a relatively new vibrational spectroscopy technique that is inherently capable of distinguishing interfacial molecules from those in the bulk. It demonstrates excellent surface sensitivity and has proved one of the most suitable available techniques to study the structure of interfaces and adsorption layers.⁴¹ The SFG technique is based on a second-order non-linear optical phenomenon known as sum-frequency generation. In the presence of intense electrical fields of laser beams, the oscillation of the dipole, which is induced by laser beams in interfacial molecules, gives rise to an SFG signal whose frequency is sum of the two incident laser (IR and visible) beams, while its intensity is proportional to the incident intensities:⁴⁰

$$I_{SFG}(\omega_{SFG}) \propto \left| \chi_{eff,NR} + \sum_q \frac{A_q}{\omega_{IR} - \omega_q + i\Upsilon_q} \right|^2 I_{IR}(\omega_{IR}) I_{vis}(\omega_{vis}) \quad (3)$$

where A_q is the amplitude of the vibrational mode q ; ω_{IR} and ω_q are the frequencies of the input IR and the resonance IR of the vibrational q mode, respectively; and Υ_q describes the damping coefficient of the SFG peak. The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (8) is the effective non-resonant susceptibility, which is almost invariant with frequency. The second term presents the effective resonant susceptibility, $\chi_{eff,R}^{(2)}$, of the interfacial material. Whenever the input IR frequency coincides with one of the molecular vibrations, an increase in $\chi_{eff,R}^{(2)}$, and consequently in the SFG signal, is clearly observed. By probing the IR through a range of frequencies, a vibrational spectrum of the interfacial molecules is obtained which can be deconvoluted using Eq. (8).⁴²

$\chi_{eff,R}^{(2)}$ is related to the second-order non-linear susceptibility $\chi_{ijk}^{(2)}$ by the following equation:

$$\chi_{eff}^{(2)} = [L(\omega_{SFG}) \cdot \hat{e}(\omega_{SFG})] \cdot \chi^{(2)} : [L(\omega_{Vis}) \cdot \hat{e}(\omega_{Vis})][L(\omega_{IR}) \cdot \hat{e}(\omega_{IR})] \quad (3)$$

where L is the Fresnel coefficient for the corresponding ω frequency and \hat{e} is the unit polarization vector. The tensor $\chi_{ijk}^{(2)}$ has 27 components that are reduced to the following 4 independent components in the case of an azimuthally isotropic interface:

$$\chi_{xxz}^{(2)} = \chi_{yyz}^{(2)}, \chi_{xzx}^{(2)} = \chi_{yzy}^{(2)}, \chi_{zxx}^{(2)} = \chi_{zyy}^{(2)}, \chi_{zzz}^{(2)} \quad (3)$$

where x , y , and z are the laboratory coordinates. These components can be selectively determined by experimental measurement of $\chi_{eff,R}^{(2)}$ values under four different polarization combinations of *ssp*, *sps*, *pss*, and *ppp* (where the first, second, and third letters represent the SFG beam, the visible beam, and the IR beam, respectively).⁴⁰

$\chi_{ijk}^{(2)}$ is, in turn, proportional to both the number density of oscillators that contribute to the signal, N , and the molecular hyper-polarizability averaged over all molecular orientations, $\langle \beta_{lmn} \rangle$, at the interface:⁴⁰

$$\chi_{ijk}^{(2)} = N \sum_{lmn} \langle \mu_{ijk:lmn} \rangle \beta_{lmn} \quad (3)$$

β_{lmn} is a tensor whose elements are defined in molecular coordinates (l, m, n); for certain molecular vibrations of certain symmetry, only a few non-zero elements of β_{lmn} exist. The matrix $\langle \mu_{ijk:lmn} \rangle$ is the orientationally-averaged Euler angle transformation from the lab coordinates to the molecular coordinates. Obtaining the SFG spectra under two different polarization combinations for an interfacial layer of surfactants with constant composition (i.e. $(\Gamma)_{ssp} = (\Gamma)_{ppp}$), the ratio $\chi_{zzz,as}^{(2)} / \chi_{yyz,s}^{(2)}$ should thus become a function of only molecular tilt angle, θ , as implied by Eq. (11). The $\chi_{zzz,as}^{(2)} / \chi_{yyz,s}^{(2)}$ ratio is determinable through applying Fresnel coefficient corrections (Eq. (9)) to the experimentally measured $\chi_{ppp}^{(2)} / \chi_{ssp}^{(2)}$ ratio. Therefore, any change in the value of $\chi_{ppp}^{(2)} / \chi_{ssp}^{(2)}$ with surfactant bulk concentration could be attributed to the orientational changes of the surfactants within the adsorption layer:⁴³

$$\left(\frac{\chi_{ppp}^{(2)}}{\chi_{ssp}^{(2)}} \right)_c = f(\theta) \quad (3)$$

2.2. Drainage kinetics and stability of TLFs

Thin liquid films (TLFs) are layers of liquid confined between two bulk phases. The bulk phases can be gaseous, as in foams (approaching bubbles), or liquid, as in emulsions, or solid, as in suspensions. TLFs form under dynamic conditions and are considered as unstable structures. To stabilize them, surfactants should adsorb at their interfaces in order to modify the surface forces and interfacial rheological characteristics. In other words, the drainage kinetics and stability of TLFs are highly dependent on the physico-chemical and structural properties of adsorption layers and their investigation is of undeniable importance to our understanding of colloidal stability.⁴⁴ Starting majorly in the second half of the 20th century, the systematic study of this topic has led to the development of a well-established theory of film drainage kinetics and remarkable improvement of the experimental techniques.^{45, 46}

During the first stages of drainage when the film is relatively thick, the capillary pressure, P_c , created at the film meniscus, is the initial deriving force for film drainage:⁴⁷

$$P_c = \frac{2\sigma}{R_c} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the surface tension of the liquid phase and R_c is the radius of the liquid surface meniscus or the internal radius of the film holder in a “*Scheludko Cell*”. Once the film thickness drops to ~ 300 nm,⁴⁸ surface forces come into effect and may either resist or accompany the capillary pressure depending on their nature as well as condition of the film solution. These surface forces are referred by the community to as “*disjoining pressure*”,^{49, 50} which according to the classic DLVO theory, is composed of electrostatic double layer force and van der Waals force:^{51, 52}

$$\Pi = \Pi_{el} + \Pi_{vdW} \quad (4)$$

It is believed that some non-DLVO forces including steric force,⁵³ hydration force⁵⁴ and hydrophobic force⁵⁵ may also contribute to the total disjoining pressure in TLFs. The steric and hydration forces are thought to emerge at the film thicknesses comparable to the molecular dimensions of surfactants,^{54, 56} while hydrophobic forces are more pronounced at very low surfactant concentrations.⁵⁵ The van der Waals part of disjoining pressure is expressed by:⁵⁷

$$\Pi_{vdW} = -\frac{A}{6\pi H^3} \quad (5)$$

where A is the *Hamaker-Lifshitz* constant and H is the film thickness. In relatively thick planar films stabilized by non-ionic surfactants, where the surface potential is low, the electrostatic disjoining pressure can be calculated using the weak overlap approximation:⁵⁸

$$\Pi_{el} = \Pi_0 e^{(-\kappa H)} \quad (5)$$

in this equation, κ is the Debye constant which is described as;

$$\kappa = \sqrt{\frac{2e^2 N_A C_{el}}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 k_B T}} \quad (5)$$

with e being the electronic charge, N_A the Avogadro's number and C_{el} the electrolyte concentration. ε_0 and ε_r are the permittivity of vacuum and the dielectric constant of water, respectively. k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is temperature. Π_0 in Eq. (16) is expressed by;

$$\Pi_0 = 64k_B T C_t \tanh^2 \left(\frac{e\psi_0^s}{4k_B T} \right) \quad (5)$$

where C_t and ψ_0^s are the total electrolyte concentration and surface potential, respectively.

In addition to the capillary and disjoining pressures, the velocity (or mobility) of film surface, U , which is controlled by its viscoelastic properties, has a significant impact on drainage behaviour of TLFs. The combined effect of surface forces and rheology on the thinning velocity of films, V , can be explained by *Radoev-Dimitrov-Ivanov (RDI)* model in which the effect of surface viscosity is neglected and only surface elasticity and surfactant diffusion effects are taken into account:⁵⁹

$$V = -\frac{dH}{dt} = \frac{2H^3}{3\mu R_f^2} (P_c - \Pi) f \quad (5)$$

where μ is the bulk viscosity of film liquid. R_f is the film radius and should be about 50 μm or less to ensure formation of planar films for which this model is valid. Here, f is the surface mobility factor and accounts for the rheological characteristics of the surface. For immobile surfaces ($U = 0$), $f = 1$ and Eq. (19) is reduced to *Scheludko's* model.⁶⁰ In this case, the surface tension gradient, which is created by differences in the local concentration of surfactants in the adsorption monolayer, is big enough to trigger an efficient Marangoni flow

that oppose the drainage within the film.⁴⁸ The final result is slowdown of the drainage process. For mobile surfaces ($U > 0$), $f > 1$ and is given by:

$$f = 1 + \frac{6\mu}{HE_G} \left(D_s + \frac{DH}{2} \frac{dC}{d\Gamma} \right) \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (20), $d\Gamma/dC$ represents the so-called adsorption length and is easily extracted from adsorption isotherm plots. D_s is the surface diffusion coefficient of surfactants in adsorption monolayer and can be affected by factors like intermolecular interaction between surfactant chains or the immersion of surfactant heads in sublayer region. D represents the bulk diffusion coefficient and for cylindrical molecules is given by:⁶¹

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\mu L} \ln \left(\frac{L}{d} \right) \quad (6)$$

with L and d representing the length and cross sectional area of a cylindrical molecule.

E_G in Eq. (20) is the *Gibbs elasticity* of surface and is actually the tangential force generating the Marangoni effect. For an interface, it is defined as the variation of interfacial tension with changing the interface area, S :¹

$$E_G = \frac{d\sigma}{d \ln S} = -\Gamma \frac{d\sigma}{d\Gamma} \quad (6)$$

Gibbs elasticity is indirectly obtainable from the equilibrium surface tension data. However, direct measurement of surface elasticity modulus has been made possible by the advent of oscillating bubble/drop methods which allow investigation of dynamic behaviour of fluid interfaces and adsorption layers. For an oscillating surface, when the surfactant exchange between bulk and adsorption layer is controlled by diffusion, the complex dilatational modulus of surface, E , is expressed by the *Lucassen – van den Temple* theory:⁶²

$$E = E_r + iE_i \quad (7)$$

with E_r and E_i being the surface dilatational elasticity and dilatational viscosity moduli, respectively:

$$E_r = E_0 \frac{1 + \Omega}{1 + 2\Omega + 2\Omega^2} \quad (8)$$

$$E_i = E_0 \frac{\Omega}{1 + 2\Omega + 2\Omega^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\Omega = \frac{dC}{d\Gamma} \sqrt{\frac{D}{2\omega}} \quad (10)$$

where ω is the surface oscillation frequency and $E_0 \equiv E_G$.

It is believed that the van der Waals disjoining pressure term in Eq. (14) is negligible for relatively thick liquid films and Π_{el} is the only force contributing to film stability. Therefore, by combining Eqs. (19) and (20) and replacing P_c and Π from Eqs. (23) and (16), final form of the equation for film drainage velocity is obtained:

$$V = -\frac{dH}{dt} = \frac{2H^3}{3\mu R_f^2} \left[\frac{2\sigma}{R_c} - \Pi_0 e^{-\kappa H} \right] \left[1 + \frac{3\mu}{E_G} \left(\frac{2D_s}{H} + D \frac{dC}{d\Gamma} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

in the next step, this equation is matched against the experimental data collected from TLF drainage measurements using micro-interferometry technique.

Micro-interferometry of TLFs has been frequently used to successfully measure the temporal variation of draining film thickness with an accuracy of ca. 0.5 nm.^{45, 63} The method was developed in the early 20th century to study the stratification in liquid films^{64, 65} and was later improved by others during decades.^{45, 66} The details of an interferometry setup are covered elsewhere.^{63, 67} Briefly, the setup is composed of a film holder ring with internal diameter of R_c located horizontally within a closed cell called “*Scheludko Cell*”. The glass ring is connected to a nano-pump or micro-syringe through a side capillary tube to enable the experimenter to easily pump the liquid into or out of the film. White or monochromatic light is shone onto the film and the reflected light intensity is measured. Once the thickness of TLF is only few hundred nanometers, an interference pattern, i.e. fringes or newton rings, appears and is recorded using an inverted microscope coupled with a CCD camera. The intensity and order of interference varies as film drains. The recorded images are then digitized in order to extract the relative values of the minimum (I_{\min}) and maximum (I_{\max}) intensities for the reflected light. Some interferometers use photomultiplier tubes to directly measure the light intensities. These information are then employed to calculate the thickness of film at any single moment of the drainage process using the following equation:⁶⁷

$$H = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi n_f} \left(l\pi \pm \arcsin \sqrt{\frac{I - I_{\min}}{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}} \right) \quad (11)$$

where λ and n_f are the wavelength of the light and refractive index of the liquid forming the film, respectively. $l = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ is the order of the interference which varies during film drainage. The $H - t$ plots obtained in this way are then matched against the theoretical predictions, i.e. Eq. (27), in order to extract the kinetic information about draining TLFs.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Materials

MIBC and *n*-pentanol were purchased from ACROS Organics and Sigma-Aldrich, respectively. *N*-hexanol was obtained from Fluka. All alcohols were 99+ % pure. All solutions were prepared using purified water, prepared by an Ultrapure Milli-Q unit from Millipore, USA. All glassware were decontaminated by immersing in an alkaline ethanol/water solution for 10 minutes and then rinsing with 1% hydrochloric acid solution and finally, flushing vigorously with DI water. All experiments were performed at the constant temperature of 23 ± 1 °C.

3.2. Tensiometry and surface elasticity measurements

The static surface tension of the solutions was measured using Wilhelmy plate method. Any possible organic contaminants on the Pt plate were burnt using a micro-beam flame until the Pt turned bright. Tabulated surface tension of deionized water at the same room temperature was used to calibrate each set of the measurements. Three successive measurements were taken and averaged for each point. Solutions were left in the measurement vessel for 5 minutes to ensure the equilibrium between the adsorption layer and bulk solution is established. Thermodynamic data were extracted by fitting the measured values to *Langmuir – Szyszkowski* model:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 + RT\Gamma_{\infty} \ln \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma_{\infty}} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\Gamma(C) = \Gamma_{\infty} \frac{C}{B + C} \quad (13)$$

where σ_0 is the surface tension of pure water; R the gas constant; Γ_{∞} the maximum adsorption of alcohols in the monolayer, and Γ is the surfactant adsorption, B is the inverted equilibrium adsorption constant and C is the surfactant bulk concentration¹³. The value of the maximal adsorption Γ_{∞} can be derived by means of the Gibbs adsorption isotherm (Eq.(1)) applied on the surface tension isotherm in the region of CMC. Hence, the model of Langmuir-Szyszkowski contains only one fitting parameter – the coefficient B . The latter represents the optimal concentration c_{opt} (see Eq.(1)) of the surfactant inside of the foam lamellae, at which the Gibbs elasticity value has maximum and the transient foam reaches maximal stability.

A profile analysis tensiometer (PAT-1, Sinterface) was employed to measure the dynamic surface tension and viscoelastic modulus on a buoyant bubble surface created in different alcohol solutions. The precise dosing system of PAT-1 allows the generation of low-amplitude harmonic perturbations of the bubble's surface area and the corresponding variations in the surface tension are recorded simultaneously. This, in turn, allows determining the viscoelastic behaviour of surface, according to Eq. (22). The bubble oscillated with varying frequencies ranging from 0.005 to 0.2 Hz. The oscillations lasted 2 hours. Three independent measurements were made for each sample in a closed cell to minimize the possible errors from evaporation or contamination.

3.3. *Foamability measurements*

Foamability of alcohols was measured using a modified Bikermann's method.⁶⁸ The used foam column (Fig. 2) had an internal diameter and height of 3.8 cm and 60 cm, respectively. 100 ml of alcohol solutions with desired concentrations was poured into the column and air with the flow rate of 30 litre per hour was passed through a porous glass disc (sparger) to create well-dispersed uniform bubbles. The volume of the foam kept increasing until it started fluctuating. This happens because of the transient nature of alcohol foams. In other words, the continuous breakdown of the bubbles at top layers of the foam creates a constant down-flow of alcohol-rich solution. This results in local concentration fluctuations within the dynamic environment of foam films in lower parts of the foam and gives rise to the

observed fluctuations in the foam volume. To avoid the consequent experimental errors, the foam volumes for all of the alcohol solutions were recorded after 10 minutes of air blowing.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the foam column used for foamability measurements

3.4. *Sum frequency generation spectroscopy*

The experimental setup and SFG methodology used in this study have been described elsewhere.⁶⁹ Briefly, the visible beam and the tunable IR were overlapped spatially and temporally on the sample. The visible beam was generated by frequency-doubling the fundamental output pulses (1064 nm, 10 Hz) of 20 ps pulse-width from an EKSPLA solid-state Nd:YAG laser. The tunable IR beam was generated from an EKSPLA optical parametric generation/amplification and difference-frequency system based on LBO and AgGaS₂ crystals. A z-cut quartz cube was used for initial optical alignment. The temperature and humidity of the laboratory were kept constant at 23±1 °C and 66±2%, respectively, to minimize the environmental errors. The geometry of the SFG setup was the same for all measurements.⁶⁹ The solutions were left in the sample holder for 5 minutes to equilibrate before recording the spectra. The SFG spectra were gathered in C-H stretching region from 2800 to 3000 cm⁻¹ under *ssp* and *ppp* polarization combinations. For each sample 5 spectra were recorded to ensure replicability of the experiments. The obtained SFG spectra were deconvoluted using the Lorentzian line-shape function described by Eq. (8).

3.5. *Micro-interferometry of thin liquid films*

The micro-interferometric measurements of TLF drainage were performed using a common “*Scheludko cell*” placed on an inverted microscope (Nikon EPIPHOT 200), coupled with a white light source. 3 ml of each alcohol solution was poured into the cell and all connections were sealed very well. A horizontal thick film was initially created using a micro-syringe and the cell was left for 30 minutes to ensure thermal equilibrium with environment and saturation of the cell with water vapour. This is so important for the consistency of experiments since evaporation from film surface can contribute significant errors to the measurements. In addition, thermal convection within the films can cause unacceptable variations in film radius or even complete film shrinkage during drainage. Once equilibrated, film liquid was sucked out slowly until the first interference fringe appeared. To ensure the formation of planar films, small films with radii from 40 to 60 μm were created and then allowed to drain under capillary forces until reaching their critical film thickness. The time period spanning film formation to its rupture was considered as the film lifetime. As drainage proceeded, the interferograms were recorded using a CCD video camera (Canon PSA640). The recorded frames were then digitized, monochromated with green light filter ($\lambda = 546 \text{ nm}$) and analysed by ImageJ software to extract the light intensities. The extracted intensities were finally put into Eq. (28) to calculate the film thicknesses at any single moment of the drainage.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. *Static and dynamic surface tension and adsorption isotherms of alcohol solutions*

Low molecular weight alcohols exhibit a considerable surface activity which is capable of reducing water surface tension to the values as low as 30 - 40 mN/m (Fig 3). Such surface activity and tensiometric behaviour, albeit exhibiting some differences in surface tension plots, are comparable to that of conventional surfactants. The agreement between our results and those reported by others is clearly excellent. We employed the Eqs. (29) and (30) to extract the value of B and Eq. (1) to derive the value of Γ_{∞} for all alcohols. According to the results listed in Table 1, n -hexanol is expectedly the most surface active of all three

alcohols. The smaller B value for MIBC than for n -pentanol shows its higher tendency towards air|water interface. However, its maximum adsorption is the smallest of all three alcohols, probably because of possessing the largest cross sectional area of carbon chain (Fig. 1).

Figure 3. Static surface tension vs alcohol concentration plots for aqueous solutions of (a) *n*-pentanol (data reported by (●) us and (□) Hey et. al⁷⁰), (b) MIBC (data reported by (●) us, (□) Comley et. al⁷¹ and (Δ) Khoshdast et. al⁷²) and (c) *n*-hexanol (data reported by (●) us and (□) Phan et. al⁷³). The black solid line is the fitting curve using *Langmuir-Szyszkowski* equation (Eq. (29)). The red solid line shows the surface excess of alcohols calculated using *Langmuir isotherm* (Eq. (30)). The vertical dashed lines represent the monolayer saturation concentrations (C_{MS}) determined by SFG spectroscopy.

Table 1. Adsorption parameters extracted from surface tension plot using *Langmuir – Szyszkowski* equation (Eq. (29)) and GAI (Eq.(1), and the value of Gibbs elasticity at c_{opt} and and the average thickness between the bubbles 10 μm . Monolayer saturation concentration (C_{MS}) was determined by SFG spectroscopy. De-foaming threshold (C_{DT}) is where the foam volume in foamability measurements starts decreasing. Γ_m^{MSC} is the surface excess in the topmost monolayer at C_{MS} point determined by SFG spectroscopy.

Alcohols	Γ_∞ ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$)	Γ_m^{MSC} ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$)	B (mM)	Water solubility at 20°C (mM)	C_{MS} (mM)	C_{DT} (mM)	$\frac{C_{DT}}{c_{opt}}$	$E_g(c_{opt})$ (mN/m)
<i>n</i> - Pentanol	4.64 ± 0.1	4.85	5.66	$\sim 250^a$	~ 60	~ 58	9.50	0.89
MIBC	4.27 ± 0.13	4.10	2.63	$\sim 150^a$	~ 20	~ 20	6.60	1.56
<i>n</i> - Hexanol	5.46 ± 0.1	5.90	2.25	$\sim 60^a$	~ 35	~ 34	12.38	2.87

^a Data extracted from the MSDS provided by chemical suppliers

One can see in Table 1 that the values of Γ_∞ determined by GAI are close to the values of the surface excess Γ_m^{MSC} in the topmost monolayer at C_{MS} point determined by SFG spectroscopy. Moreover, one can see the level of depletion in the foam lamellae for the cases of the three particular surfactants. The level of surfactant depletion in the foam lamella as compared to the surfactant into the aqueous solution is approximately an order of magnitude. Moreover, one can see that the Gibbs elasticity values at c_{opt} in the foam lamellae increase in the order pentanol, MIBC, Hexanol. Hence, the foam stabilized by these surfactants increases its stability in the same order.

For all alcohols, the adsorption increases with bulk concentration, implying that the adsorption monolayer does not reach full saturation within the studied concentration range. In the case of conventional surfactants, appearance of a CMC point is traditionally interpreted as the saturation of surface because the unavailability of more space for monomeric surfactants forces them to aggregate inside the bulk rather than further migrate to the surface. Thus, surface tension remains nearly constant beyond CMC³. This idea is in fact debatable since surfactants are believed to also form pre-micelles at concentrations much lower than CMC.⁷⁴

The pre-micellization process may be reflected in the form of small kinks and additional plateaus in static surface tension plots.³⁴ It is also discussed that surface may not be fully saturated even at concentrations up to 10 times of CMC.¹¹ The absence of kinks and CMCs in Fig. 3, can therefore be interpreted as the absence of pre-micellization and micellization for these small alcohols. This observation agrees well with previous reports.⁷⁵ In spite of some claims, no experimental evidence exists for the micellization of these small molecules. Their relatively high solubility and short carbon chains in comparison to conventional surfactants make it difficult for them to efficiently attract each other and aggregate. We however admit that formation of smaller aggregates such as dimers, trimers, etc. remains a possibility. Besides, it is impossible to identify the topmost monolayer saturation concentration (C_{MS}) from tensiometry. To avoid the abovementioned arguments and difficulties, we studied the state of adsorption layers of these alcohols independently of the bulk, using the surface-specific SFG spectroscopy. Further discussion regarding this issue is made in the next section.

We will also discuss that the drainage kinetics and foamability are measured under dynamic conditions which may interrupt the equilibrium state between adsorption layers and the underlying bulk solution. Wilhelmy tensiometry and SFG spectroscopy however measure the equilibrium state of adsorption layers. One may wonder how we correlate the equilibrium state data with those measured under dynamic conditions. To ensure the consistency and reliability of the results, it is therefore important to understand how fast the equilibrium is regained under dynamic conditions of interface. This was easily investigated by measuring the dynamic surface tension on a buoyant bubble. Fig. 4 demonstrates the outcome for *n*-hexanol solutions. The data obtained for the other two alcohols are also provided in Fig. S1 (see supplementary information). For all samples, the agreement between static and dynamic surface tension values is excellent. According to the well-known *Ward-Tordai* theory of adsorption kinetics, which assumes a diffusion-controlled adsorption mechanism,⁷⁶ the time evolution of surface tension for non-ionic surfactant solutions can be explained by:⁷⁷

$$\sigma(t)_{t \rightarrow \infty} = \sigma_{eq} + \frac{RT\Gamma^2}{2C} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{Dt}} \quad (14)$$

where R and T are the gas constant and temperature of the solution, respectively. D is the bulk diffusion coefficient. C is bulk surfactant concentration. Γ is surface excess of surfactant and σ_{eq} denotes the surface tension at equilibrium and corresponds to the plateau in a

dynamic surface tension plot. For larger surfactants where the diffusion coefficients are relatively small when compared with these alcohols, the second term in the right hand of Eq. (31) takes large values. In other terms, the initial surface tension right after expansion of the bubble surface is considerably higher than its equilibrium value; it hence takes some time for surface tension to recover from the perturbation.³⁴ Here, the initial surface tensions are however the same as their equilibrium values and do not evolve over time, implying that these alcohols are fast-adsorbing and equilibrium is readily regained in adsorption layers. We thus expect a good correlation between the data obtained under equilibrium or dynamic conditions. The small size of the alcohols justifies their greater diffusion coefficients. This is discussed also in *Section 4.4*.

Figure 4. Dynamic Surface tension data obtained for different concentrations of *n*-hexanol.

4.2. Sum frequency generation spectroscopy of absorption layers

The recorded SFG spectra of all alcohols in C-H stretching region were normalised for IR and visible laser intensities and are depicted in Fig. 5. Qualitatively, the intensity of major peaks increases with bulk concentration of the alcohols. The recorded *ssp* spectra for *n*-pentanol and *n*-hexanol are similar to a large extent but different from MIBC spectrum in some spectral features. The differences in the *ppp* spectral features seem very small within the experimental errors. To be more specific, we used Eq. (8) to de-convolute the spectra to individual peaks. The spectral features in a SFG spectrum can be assigned to different vibrational modes of molecular moieties through comparison to the corresponding IR and Raman spectra. Contrary to the OH spectral regime, there is a consensus within the

community about the peak assignments in C-H stretching region, despite the small shifts in vibrational frequencies originating from the differences in molecular structures and environment. Commonly, the peak at 2855 – 2860 cm^{-1} is assigned to the *symmetric stretch* of CH_2 (d^+) which weakened and shifted down to 2836 – 2840 cm^{-1} in the case of MIBC. The *asymmetric stretch* of CH_2 (d^-) appears at 2925 – 2931 cm^{-1} . The peak at 2900 – 2910 is attributed to the *Fermi resonance* of CH_2 symmetric stretches (d_{FR}^+). Similarly for CH_3 , the *symmetric stretch* (r^+) appears at 2875 – 2880 cm^{-1} ; the *asymmetric stretch* (r^-) around 2965 cm^{-1} and the *Fermi resonance* of the symmetric stretch (r_{FR}^+) around 2946 cm^{-1} .^{40, 43} The individual peaks and their extracted features for a 20 mM solution of MIBC are provided in Fig. 6 and Table 2, respectively. The spectral fitting results for the other solutions are also provided in supplementary information (see Tables S1, S2 and S3).

Figure 5. CH regime SF spectra recorded for different concentrations of (top) *n*-pentanol, (middle) MIBC and (bottom) *n*-hexanol under (left) *ssp* and (right) *ppp* polarisation combinations. The coloured solid lines are the best fits calculated using Eq. (8). The SF intensities are normalised for IR and visible laser intensities. The spectra are offset by different values for clarity.

Figure 6. De-convolution of the recorded SFG spectra for a 20 mM MIBC solution under *ssp* and *ppp*

Peak assignment	ω_q (cm ⁻¹)	<i>ssp</i>		<i>ppp</i>	
		A_q	Υ_q	A_q	Υ_q
CH ₂ ν_s (d^+)	2838	38.67	6.56	14.97	5.24
CH ₃ ν_s (r^+)	2875	468.99	7.44	55.67	7.73
CH ₂ ν_{as} (d^-)	2925	8.45	3.98	38.47	6.59
CH ₃ ν_{as} (r^-)	2966	109.19	7.28	378.98	7.69
CH ₂ ν_{FR} (d_{FR}^+)	2905	-116.58	3.88	35.67	5.56
CH ₃ ν_{FR} (r_{FR}^+)	2947	392.09	10.25	99.78	9.60

polarisation combinations.

Table 2. Spectral features extracted from the spectral fitting for a 20 mM MIBC solution.

A detailed scrutiny of the spectral and the corresponding structural differences are not within the scope of this paper, nor is the orientation calculation of the adsorbed alcohol molecules. Qualitatively, all *ppp* spectra are dominated by the *asymmetric stretch* of methyl groups at around 2965 cm⁻¹. The *ssp* spectrum of MIBC is dominated by the vibrational modes of methyl groups only. MIBC molecule bears three terminal methyl groups but only one methylene group. On the contrary, a small peak assigned to the symmetric stretch of methylene groups around 2855 cm⁻¹ appears in the *ssp* spectra of both *n*-pentanol and *n*-hexanol whose molecules have 4 and 5 methylene groups, respectively (Fig. 1). On the other

hand, the weak shoulder at 2965 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to the *asymmetric stretch* of methyl groups, disappears. This is believed to originate from the conformational changes of molecules. In a hydrocarbon chain with “*all-trans*” conformation, all methylene groups have a local centro-symmetry. The theory of sum frequency generation predicts that centrosymmetrically positioned molecular moieties will cancel out the SF signal from each other. Thus, the spectrum should be mainly dominated by the methyl stretches. When the hydrocarbon chain adopts a “*gauche*” conformation, the local centro-symmetry is disrupted, rendering the methylene groups SFG-detectable. *Gauche* defects however randomize the orientation of methyl groups and weaken their SF intensities. Depending on the degree of *gauche* defects, the spectrum can therefore be dominated by methyl or methylene stretches.⁴⁰ The *ssp* spectra for *n*-pentanol and *n*-hexanol feature both CH_2 and CH_3 stretches, implying moderate *gauche* defects for these short-chained alcohols. Longer surfactants are known to undergo significant *gauche* to *trans* conformational transformations by going from low to high surface coverage.⁷⁸ This phenomenon may cause large variations in the average orientation of molecules, and hence, in the overall SF signal intensity (Eq. (11)). In that case, the contribution of the molecular density to SF signal could be difficult to distinguish. Fortunately, such a conformational transformation is not remarkable for the studied alcohols since the relative intensities of methyl and methylene symmetrical stretches do not change much with alcohol concentration (Fig. 5).

From the spectral fitting we extracted the absolute values of susceptibilities for both polarisation combinations as well as their ratios at each alcohol concentration, as demonstrated in Fig. 7. In the absence of conformational transformation, any change in the susceptibility should originate from the change of number density and/or tilt angle of the adsorbed alcohol molecules, according to Eq. (11). A change in molecular tilt angle can easily be tracked from the trend of $\chi_{ppp}^{(2)} / \chi_{ssp}^{(2)}$ (Eq. (12)). Fig. 7 shows that this ratio varies

only slightly at low to medium alcohol concentrations and immediately becomes constant at about 35 mM, 15 mM and 10 mM bulk concentrations of *n*-pentanol, MIBC and *n*-hexanol, respectively. These small molecules, unlike conventional surfactants, do not seem to undergo considerable orientational changes with surface coverage, probably because of smaller steric effects, moderate conformational defects and weaker intermolecular interactions between their short hydrocarbon chains. Therefore, the continuing occupation of

adsorption monolayer by alcohol molecules has the major contribution to the observed signal increase. At higher concentrations the adsorbed molecules are orientationally stable.

Figure 7. Variation of (Δ) $\chi_{ssp}^{(2)}$, (\blacksquare) $\chi_{ppp}^{(2)}$ and (\bullet) $\chi_{ppp}^{(2)} / \chi_{ssp}^{(2)}$ values with alcohol concentration in aqueous solutions of (top) *n*-pentanol, (middle) MIBC and (bottom) *n*-hexanol extracted from spectral de-convolution of the corresponding SFG spectra.

It is also obvious that $\chi^{(2)}$ values keep increasing up to the concentrations of 60 mM for *n*-pentanol; 20 mM for MIBC; and 35 mM for *n*-hexanol. $\chi^{(2)}$ finally becomes constant at these concentrations indicating that no more alcohol molecules adsorbed at the topmost adsorption monolayer. These concentrations can reasonably be considered as the points at which the topmost adsorption monolayer becomes fully saturated. Here, we refer to them as the “*monolayer saturation concentration*”, denoted by C_{MS} . The surface excess at C_{MS} , i.e. Γ_m^{MSC} , which was calculated by Langmuir isotherm, i.e. Eq. (30), was found to be smaller than the predicted maximum adsorption (Γ_∞) values (Table 1). Assuming a classical Gibbs model of interface, we would expect that the solution surface tension should have stopped decreasing at C_{MS} . For long-chain surfactants, C_{MS} should have also been nearly the same as CMC, but our method of independent identification of surface saturation clearly shows otherwise. As depicted in Fig. 3, surface tension keeps decreasing by significant amounts even after C_{MS} point. Such a surface tension drop after monolayer saturation has recently started a serious argument within the community. We have already addressed this issue in a separate paper.²⁷ In that paper we attributed the after-saturation decrease of surface tension to “*sub-monolayer adsorption*”. However, we did not investigate how the existence of sub-monolayer could affect the interfacial phenomena. An alternative explanation to the observed

contradiction could be given by assuming an actually unsaturated monolayer at C_{MS} point, if the alcohol molecules adsorbed in such a disordered way that the total contribution to SF signal would become zero. This is however not preferable by molecules since surfactant layers at high surface coverage tend to be more ordered in order to minimize the steric effects and maximize the stabilising impact of intermolecular interactions. In addition, an upside-down adsorption of alcohols at water surface is not energetically favourable because of the hydrogen bonding cancelation between the alcohol hydroxyl groups and surrounding water molecules. In the next sections, we will show that the observed peculiarities in foaming behaviour of the alcohol solutions can be successfully explained by assuming an extended model of interface, which allows for our proposed sub-monolayer adsorption.

4.3. Foamability of alcohols

The obtained foamability plots are typical to low molecular weight alcohol solutions, as demonstrated in Fig. 8. A similar trend have been reported also by others,⁶⁸ although the maximum foamability plateau did not appear for some alcohols.⁷⁹ The maximum foamability of all three alcohols are nearly the same. The initial increase in the foam volume is mainly attributed to the enhancement of surface elasticity with surfactant adsorption (Eq. (22)). The stabilising Marangoni effect is believed to grow with surface coverage and reach its maximum value at full surface saturation around CMC.⁸⁰ In addition, an increase in the electrostatic disjoining pressure, especially with ionic surfactants, will also add to the stability of foams. Nonetheless, foam stability is better understood by thin film balance (TFB) measurements (see section 4.4) than by foamability testing because of the dynamic environment of the foam films in a foam column. The origin of the plateau in foamability plot is not known yet. Perhaps, the dynamic nature of foam films within the foam column causes local variations in alcohol concentration. Because of the transient nature of alcohol foams, there is a significant downflow of alcohol-rich solution from the bubble break-up taking place in the upper layers of the foam that probably adds to the local alcohol concentration within the films.

Figure 8. The measured foamability of (■) *n*-pentanol, (▲) MIBC and (●) *n*-hexanol solutions versus alcohol concentration. The vertical lines show the bulk alcohol concentrations at which the topmost surface monolayer is completely saturated (C_{MS}), as determined directly using SFG Spectroscopy. The air flow rate was 30 litre per hour.

At high concentrations, the foamability sharply drops for all alcohols. The slopes of this part of the foamability plots are in the same order as the hydrophobicity of alcohols; *n*-hexanol > MIBC > *n*-pentanol. In a rather qualitative manner, this behaviour has been attributed to either the limited solubility of alcohols or micellization of conventional surfactants.^{68, 79, 80} Here, the concentration at which foamability starts decreasing is called “*de-foaming threshold*” and is denoted by C_{DT} . Table 1 shows that the obtained C_{DT} values are much smaller than the reported solubility of alcohols at 20°C. In other words, de-foaming happens well within the solubility range of the alcohols. In section 4.1, we discussed that pre-micellization and micellization does not take place for these short-chain alcohols. On the other hand, the comparison of C_{DT} with C_{MS} values reveals that the foam volume drops immediately after the full surface saturation that was independently detected using SFG spectroscopy (see section 4.2). Such an excellent agreement between C_{DT} and C_{MS} values cannot be a random coincidence. The sharp decrease in foamability of the alcohols therefore seems to be caused by the proposed sub-monolayer adsorption. In the absence of micellization and once the surface is already saturated, the only available place for the alcohol molecules in order to minimize their unfavourable contact with the surrounding water is the sub-monolayer region. Although the foamability measurements provide additional

evidence for the existence of the proposed sub-monolayer adsorption, it does not give any clue about its interaction mechanism with the topmost adsorption monolayer.

4.3. *TLF drainage kinetics*

We have to admit that our measurements on foam films with thickness in the range of 30 nm – 250 nm corresponds to significantly dryer foams, while the foam, which we have studied are relatively wet and with average distance between the bubbles of 1 μm and more. Nevertheless, these experiments give us valuable information about the properties of the foam film surfaces and the located on them surfactant adsorption layers.

Thus, we studied the kinetics and drainage behaviour of TLFs of these alcohols using micro-interferometry. To create planar films and ensure uniform drainage we tried to keep the film radii around 50 μm (Fig. 9). The equilibrium film thickness (H_{eq}) is plotted against bulk alcohol concentration in Fig. 10. H_{eq} linearly increases with alcohol concentration up to C_{MS} (or C_{DT}) where surface becomes fully saturated and then drops sharply. No stable films were obtained for 40 mM MIBC, 50 mM *n*-hexanol and 90 mM *n*-pentanol solutions and drainage ended with film rupture. The effect of sub-monolayer adsorption on TLF thickness and stability is therefore tremendous. As film thinning proceeds, according to Eq. (19), the overlap between the electrical double layers of both surfaces increases and the repulsive electrostatic disjoining pressure becomes greater. The thinning velocity, which is also highly dependent on the rheological characteristics of the surface, therefore keeps decreasing until reaching zero at equilibrium. In other words, the film rests at equilibrium once the disjoining pressure equals the capillary pressure. The higher the surface potential (or the lower the capillary pressure) is, the faster the equilibrium is reached and the larger H_{eq} becomes. By increasing the bulk concentration, the surface is continuously occupied by the alcohol molecules. This will decrease the capillary pressure because of the significant reduction in surface tension (Eq. (13)) on one hand, and will also promote the electrostatic disjoining pressure created by the partial charge on hydroxyl groups of the alcohols, on the other hand. In addition, the progressively improving elasticity of the surface will result in a bigger Marangoni flow that resists drainage. The overall effect is the observed increase in H_{eq} with bulk alcohol concentration. The larger surface excess of *n*-pentanol and *n*-hexanol in

comparison to MIBC (Table 1) is probably the reason for their relatively thicker films at equilibrium.

Figure 9. Sample interferograms recorded during the drainage of a thin film created in a 20 mM solution of MIBC.

Based on the tensiometry results (Fig. 3), the solution surface tension and the resulting capillary pressure should keep decreasing throughout the whole studied concentration range including both monolayer and sub-monolayer adsorption regimes. Also, the continuous adsorption of alcohols within the interfacial region should increase rather than decrease the electrostatic disjoining pressure. A diminishing surface potential with the addition of non-ionic alcohol molecules is inconceivable. By assuming a Gibbs model of dividing surface, i.e. monolayer adsorption, the elasticity of surface would be expected to keep improving with alcohol concentration (Eq. (22)). All these factors should have yielded a constant increase in H_{eq} with bulk concentration. Unexpectedly, H_{eq} was observed to sharply drop soon after C_{MS} (or C_{DT}) points. This indicates an obvious shortcoming of the classical Gibbs convention and also implies that the sub-monolayer adsorption influences the surface rheology rather than the surface forces in an unconventional way. Thus, we focused our study on the surface rheology of films below and beyond the topmost monolayer saturation in order to understand the de-foaming mechanism of sub-monolayer adsorption.

Figure 10. Equilibrium thickness (H_{eq}) of thin liquid films stabilized with various concentrations of (■) *n*-pentanol, (▲) MIBC and (●) *n*-hexanol. The values were determined interferometrically. The symbols in green show the film thicknesses at rupture (H_R).

As we discussed in section 2.2, the RDI theory of TLF drainage kinetics assumes that drainage velocity is only influenced by surfactant diffusion and surface elasticity. The effect of surface viscosity is presumably negligible. Prior to application of RDI theory, i.e. Eq. (27), to our drainage data, we investigated the validity of this assumption by measuring the viscoelastic modulus for all alcohol solutions. Fig. 11 shows that the dilatational viscosity is almost zero at low frequency range and thus negligible for all alcohols at the studied concentrations. RDI theory was then used reliably to study the drainage kinetics of the TLFs. The measured elasticities do not vary much with frequency except for 0.2 Hz where there is a slight increase for some solutions. This is because of the fast-diffusing nature of alcohol molecules as also predicted by dynamic surface tension results in section 4.1. At high frequencies alcohol molecules do not have enough time to diffuse and eliminate the created surface tension gradient and the elasticities rise because of the bigger surface tension gradient (see Eq. (22)). In general, surface elasticities have comparatively bigger values at concentrations below than above C_{MS} . MIBC solutions have the largest measured elasticities probably because of its smaller diffusion coefficient as predicted by Eq. (21). For all alcohols, the dilatational elasticity considerably drops right after or at full monolayer saturation, implying an increase in the surface mobility, f , according to Eq. (20). The surface mobility and elasticity are governed by the surface tension gradient which is the driving force for the Marangoni effect. It seems that sub-monolayer affects surface rheology through reducing the stabilising effect of Marangoni stress. This means that sub-monolayer region

compensates for the surface tension gradient at the topmost monolayer created by the surface expansion. Equation 20 expresses that faster diffusion of surfactants at surface and/or from bulk to surface would lead to a larger surface mobility because the surface tension gradient would be diminished or eliminated by the further adsorption of surfactants at the fresh surface created during expansion. Therefore, we hypothesize that sub-monolayer adsorption should somehow have an increasing effect on the diffusion characteristics of alcohol molecules. We tested this hypothesis by conducting TLF drainage experiments in order to determine D and D_s values.

Figure 11. Dilatational viscoelasticity modulus (E_r and E_i) measured for different concentrations of (a) *n*-pentanol, (b) MIBC and (c) *n*-hexanol solutions at various frequencies.

One can see that the values of the elastic moduli in Fig.11 are in the order of magnitude of Gibbs elasticity values calculated by Eq. (1) (see Table 1).

The drainage behaviour of TLFs were obtained interferometrically using Scheludko cell. The drainage velocities were then calculated from the slopes of drainage plots. Fig. 12 demonstrates the results at three different concentrations; before monolayer saturation; at full monolayer saturation; and after monolayer saturation or sub-monolayer adsorption region. Qualitatively, drainage slows down by reaching full monolayer saturation and afterwards increases sharply under the influence of sub-monolayer adsorption. This accords well with the foamability observations where the foam volume dropped right after monolayer saturation. The elimination of surface tension gradient by sub-monolayer alcohol molecules seems to have increased the surface mobility and hence the drainage velocity of foam films. The solid lines in Fig. 12 are the fits to experimental data which were calculated using Eq. (27). For all solutions, the Debye length of distilled water was used which is 152 nm for a 4 μ M solution of 1:1 electrolytes. This weak ionic strength is generated by water autoprotolysis and CO₂ dissolution.⁴⁸ A bulk viscosity of 932.1 μ Pa.s was used for all solutions at 23°C. The surface tension and adsorption length values were extracted from the surface tension plots in Fig. 3. Care should however be taken when using Gibbs elasticity values extracted from surface tension isotherms. In Fig. S2 of supplementary information we have provided the calculated E_G values. These values are significantly smaller than the measured dilatational elasticities in Fig. 11.

Gibbs elasticity, which is extracted from static surface tension plots, gives the elasticity of a surface at equilibrium state where the adsorption-desorption of surfactants has no effect on the overall surface tension. In a dynamic environment where the surface area, and accordingly, the interfacial distribution of surfactants change, diffusion characteristics have a significant impact on the rheological characteristics of the surface. When the surface expansion frequency is high enough, surface becomes purely elastic. In this case there is not enough time for surfactant molecules to diffuse from bulk to the surface and eliminate the created surface tension gradient. According to Eqs. (24) and (26), the measured elasticity

modulus should then become equal to the Gibbs elasticity of the surface. However, considerable deviations from Gibbs elasticity have been reported even at high frequencies which have been attributed to the effect of subsurface adsorption layer²⁵ or the compressibility of surfactant layer.⁸¹ Here, we used the directly measured dilatational elasticity rather than Gibbs elasticity since it provides a better estimation of the surface elasticity under dynamic conditions.

Figure 12. (Left panels) the measured drainage behaviour and (right panels) the calculated drainage velocities of TLFs for different concentrations of (a) *n*-pentanol, (b) MIBC and (c) *n*-hexanol solutions. The lines are fits to Eq. (27).

Table 3. Π_0 , D_s and D values extracted from fitting of Eq. (27) to the experimental drainage data measured by interferometry of different alcohol solution TLFs.

Alcohols	Concentration (mM)	$\ln \Pi_0$ (Pa)	D_s ($\times 10^{10}$ m ² /s)	D ($\times 10^{10}$ m ² /s)
<i>n</i> -pentanol	20	9.6	11.4	8.1
	60	10.8	10.3	7.7
	80	11.5	19.2	13.5
MIBC	10	8.9	11.3	5.6
	20	9.4	9.8	5.1
	40	10.6	23.2	9.8
<i>n</i> -hexanol	5	9.5	11	7.8
	35	11.1	9.5	8.0
	50	11.6	20.1	14.1

Π_0 , D and D_s , which are the fitting parameters in Eq. (27), were determined and are listed in Table 3. The bulk diffusion coefficients are deviated from those measured experimentally.⁸² D_s is approximated to be 1.5 times the bulk diffusion coefficient but is smaller here.⁸³ It should be noted that these values are not experimentally-determined but fitting values. Any factor contributing to the experimental errors during interferometry and image analysis processes will also affect the final values of diffusion coefficients. In addition, D_s can be influenced by the immersion and intermolecular interaction of surfactants in adsorption layers. According to Table 3, the surface disjoining pressure continuously increases with alcohol concentration. Diffusion coefficients slightly decrease at C_{MS} presumably because of the growing interaction of molecules at surface and within the bulk. However, they increase significantly right after monolayer saturation. As we expected and discussed above, sub-monolayer adsorption facilitates the diffusion of surfactants which leads to the fast elimination of surface tension gradient and a diminishing Marangoni stress. This phenomena is explained by considering the sub-monolayer region as an immediate supplement of alcohol molecules. When surface expands in the absence of sub-monolayer adsorption, alcohol molecules should diffuse from both bulk of the solution and other parts of the surface in order to compensate for the created surface tension gradient. In the presence of sub-monolayer alcohols, this process is much faster as alcohol molecules can immediately

adsorb from the underlying sub-monolayer region. In this case the drainage kinetics is controlled by the diffusion of alcohol molecules from sub-monolayer to monolayer ($D_{sm \rightarrow m}$) rather than from bulk to monolayer. This process is illustrated schematically in Fig. 13. The sub-monolayer region actually functions as a buffer layer to keep the surfactant density of the topmost monolayer constant. The consequence of such a function is a considerable reduction in surface tension gradient, surface elasticity and Marangoni effect at the topmost monolayer as well as the enhancement of surface mobility.

Fig 13. (Left) in the absence of sub-monolayer adsorption, the Marangoni stress is compensated for by diffusion of alcohol molecules from both surface, D_s , and bulk of the solution, D . (Right) in the presence of sub-monolayer alcohols, the Marangoni stress is reduced by the immediate diffusion of alcohol molecules from the underlying sub-monolayer to the topmost monolayer, $D_{sm \rightarrow m}$, giving rise to a buffering effect on surface tension gradient.

5. Conclusion

The full saturation of the topmost adsorption layer was independently determined by SFG spectroscopy. By comparing to surface tension data, we found that surface tension kept decreasing even after monolayer saturation. This observation is not explainable by the Gibbs model of dividing surface plane. According to Gibbs convention, all surfactants who make a contribution to the solution surface tension are proposed to locate on the dividing plane. This plane is taken equivalent to the adsorption monolayer. It then becomes a mystery how

surfactants can further decrease the surface tension even after the monolayer saturation. This paradox has already caused confusion and arguments within the community. In the present work, we proposed the sub-monolayer adsorption which is justifiable by Guggenheim's model of an extended interface. In this convention, the interfacial region is considered as a separate phase with a volume and all surfactants adsorbed inside this volume can contribute to the solution surface tension. This implies that monolayer saturation will not necessarily be the end of the adsorption process and sub-monolayer adsorption can also have a significant contribution to solution surface tension. In this case, other monolayer-based isotherms like Langmuir also make inaccurate estimations of the maximum surface excess of surfactants because static surface tension do not distinguish between the monolayer and sub-monolayer.

On the contrary, the foamability, surface elasticity, and TLF drainage measurements provided supporting evidence for the existence of the proposed sub-monolayer adsorption and proved its tremendous effect on the rheological characteristics and dynamic behaviour of the surface. Thus for example, the expansion of a certain area from a foam lamellae containing surfactant sub-monolayer should not cause an increase of the surface tension value in the same spot, due to the ultra-fast transfer of the surfactant molecules from the sub-monolayer into the plane of the surfactant monolayer. This causes sudden drop in the value of the Gibbs elasticity (see Eq.(1), which should approach zero level. Thus, the foam containing surfactant sub-monolayer becomes more unstable.

Sub-monolayer region was found to have a strong buffering effect on dynamic behaviour of the topmost adsorption layer. Unfortunately, SFG spectroscopy could not probe the sub-monolayer region and its microscopic structure remains unidentified. It would be useful to understand whether the sub-monolayer alcohols are organised in the form of a well-ordered second layer or as a layer of randomly-ordered smaller aggregates, i.e. dimers, trimers, etc. Recent computer simulation snapshots of alcohol solution surfaces have revealed the formation of a second layer of alcohols beneath the topmost monolayer at high concentrations. However, this fact has not been noticed by the authors.⁸⁴ The notion of sub-monolayer adsorption is yet to be addressed appropriately by the community. We hope this work will initiate some interest among physical chemists to provide a thermodynamic explanation for this phenomena. We also see an immediate need for mathematical description of its effects on the hydrodynamics of thin liquid films.

6. Acknowledgment

This research has been supported under Australian Research Council's Projects funding schemes (project numbers DP140101089). This research was undertaken in collaboration with the scientists from Bulgarian academy of sciences during the first author's visit as a holder of a University of Queensland Graduate School International Travel Award. The University of Queensland is also acknowledged for the IPRS and Centenary postgraduate scholarships provided to the first author (AAS). Stoyan Karakashev thanks to H2020 Project Materials Networking for the financial support.

References

1. B. A. Bumstead; R. G. Van Name; Longley, W. R., *The Collected Works of J. Willard Gibbs*; Longmans, Green and Co.: New York, 1928.
2. Arthur W. Adamson; Gast, A. P., *Physical Chemistry of Surfaces*; John Wiley & Sons Inc.: New York, 1997.
3. Rosen, M. J., *Surfactants and Interfacial Phenomena*, 3rd ed.; Wiley: Chichester, UK, 2004.
4. Langmuir, I., Theory of Adsorption. *Physical Review* **1915**, *6*, 79-80.
5. Langmuir, I., The Constitution and Fundamental Properties of Solids and Liquids. II. Liquids. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1917**, *39*, 1848-1906.
6. Frumkin, A., Remarks on the Theory of Adsorption and Distribution. *Z. Physik. Chem.* **1925**, *116*, 501-3.
7. Menger, F. M.; Shi, L.; Rizvi, S. A. A., Additional Support for a Revised Gibbs Analysis. *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 1588-1589.
8. Menger, F. M.; Shi, L.; Rizvi, S. A. A., Re-Evaluating the Gibbs Analysis of Surface Tension at the Air/Water Interface. *J Am Chem Soc* **2009**, *131*, 10380-10381.
9. Menger, F. M.; Rizvi, S. A. A., Relationship between Surface Tension and Surface Coverage. *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 13975-13977.
10. Li, P. X.; Li, Z. X.; Shen, H.-H.; Thomas, R. K.; Penfold, J.; Lu, J. R., Application of the Gibbs Equation to the Adsorption of Nonionic Surfactants and Polymers at the Air–Water Interface: Comparison with Surface Excesses Determined Directly Using Neutron Reflectivity. *Langmuir* **2013**, *29*, 9324-9334.
11. Xu, H.; Li, P. X.; Ma, K.; Thomas, R. K.; Penfold, J.; Lu, J. R., Limitations in the Application of the Gibbs Equation to Anionic Surfactants at the Air/Water Surface: Sodium Dodecylsulfate and Sodium Dodecylmonooxyethylenesulfate above and Below the Cmc. *Langmuir* **2013**, *29*, 9335-9351.
12. Li, P. X.; Thomas, R. K.; Penfold, J., Limitations in the Use of Surface Tension and the Gibbs Equation to Determine Surface Excesses of Cationic Surfactants. *Langmuir* **2014**, *30*, 6739-6747.
13. Langmuir, I., The Adsorption of Gases on Plane Surfaces of Glass, Mica and Platinum. *J Am Chem Soc* **1918**, *40*, 1361-1403.
14. Frumkin, A. N., *Z Phys Chem* **1925**, *116*, 466.
15. Volmer, M., *Z Phys Chem* **1925**, *115*, 253.
16. Bartsch, O., Uber Schaumssysteme. *Fortschritteberichte uber Kolloide und Polymere* **1924**, *20*, 1-49.
17. Bartsch, O., Concerning the Formation of Foam and Surface Tension. *Kolloid-Zeitschrift* **1926**, *38*, 177-179.
18. Scheludko, A., *Khimiya, Koloidna (Colloidal Chemistry)*. 2nd Ed, 1963, p 273 pp.

19. Adam, N. K., *Physics and Chemistry of the Surfaces*; Government's publisher of scientific and technical literature: Moscow, 1947.
20. Gibbs, J. W., *The Collected Works*; Longmans: New York, 1928.
21. Scheludko, A., *Colloid Chemistry. Translated from Russian*, 1966, p 277 pp.
22. Mysels, K. J.; Cox, M. C.; Skewis, J. D., The Measurement of Film Elasticity. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1961**, *65*, 1107.
23. Kitchener, J. A., Elasticity of Soap Films; an Amendment. *Nature* **1962**, *195*, 1094.
24. Thomas, R. K.; Penfold, J., Multilayering of Surfactant Systems at the Air–Dilute Aqueous Solution Interface. *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 7440-7456.
25. Wantke, K. D.; Örtegren, J.; Fruhner, H.; Andersen, A.; Motschmann, H., The Influence of the Sublayer on the Surface Dilatational Modulus. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2005**, *261*, 75-83.
26. Wantke, K.-D.; Fruhner, H., Determination of Surface Dilational Viscosity Using the Oscillating Bubble Method. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2001**, *237*, 185-199.
27. Afshin Asadzadeh Shahir; Khoi Tan Nguyen; Nguyen, A. V., A Sum-Frequency Generation Spectroscopic Study of the Gibbs Analysis Paradox: Monolayer or Sub-Monolayer Adsorption? *Phys Chem Chem Phys* **2016**, *18*, 8794 - 8805.
28. Guggenheim, E. A., *Thermodynamics*: North Holland, Amsterdam, 1967.
29. Otis, D. R.; Ingenito, E. P.; Kamm, R. D.; Johnson, M., Dynamic Surface Tension of Surfactant Ta: Experiments and Theory. *Journal of Applied Physiology* **1994**, *77*, 2681-2688.
30. Aksenenko; Kovalchuk; Fainerman; Miller, R., Surface Dilational Rheology of Mixed Surfactants Layers at Liquid Interfaces. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2007**, *111*, 14713-14719.
31. Johnson, D. O.; Stebe, K. J., Experimental Confirmation of the Oscillating Bubble Technique with Comparison to the Pendant Bubble Method: The Adsorption Dynamics of 1-Decanol. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **1996**, *182*, 526-538.
32. Johnson, D. O.; Stebe, K. J., An Oscillating Bubble Technique to Determine Surfactant Mass Transfer Kinetics. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **1996**, *114*, 41-51.
33. Georgieva, D.; Cagna, A.; Langevin, D., Link between Surface Elasticity and Foam Stability. *Soft Matter* **2009**, *5*, 2063-2071.
34. Arabadzhiyeva, D.; Tchoukov, P.; Soklev, B.; Mileva, E., Interfacial Layer Properties and Foam Film Drainage Kinetics of Aqueous Solutions of Hexadecyltrimethylammonium Chloride. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2014**, *460*, 28-37.
35. Liu, H.; Han, P.; Sun, G.; Pan, F.; Li, B.; Wang, J.; Lv, C., Surface Dilational Rheology, Foam, and Core Flow Properties of Alpha Olefin Sulfonate. *Journal of Surfactants and Detergents* **2017**, *20*, 35-45.
36. Georgieva, D.; Schmitt, V.; Leal-Calderon, F.; Langevin, D., On the Possible Role of Surface Elasticity in Emulsion Stability. *Langmuir* **2009**, *25*, 5565-5573.
37. Rao, Y.; Li, X.; Lei, X.; Jockusch, S.; George, M. W.; Turro, N. J.; Eiseenthal, K. B., Observations of Interfacial Population and Organization of Surfactants with Sum Frequency Generation and Surface Tension. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2011**, *115*, 12064-12067.
38. J. Örtegren; K. D. Wantke; Motschmann, H., An Oscillating Bubble Device for Direct Measurement of Molecular Exchange Processes at the Air–Liquid Interface in the Medium Frequency Range. *Review of Scientific Instruments* **2003**, *74*, 5167-5172.
39. Örtegren, J.; Wantke, K.-D.; Motschmann, H.; Möhwald, H., A Study of Kinetic Molecular Exchange Processes in the Medium Frequency Range by Surface Shg on an Oscillating Bubble. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2004**, *279*, 266-276.
40. Lambert, A. G.; Davies, P. B.; Neivandt, D. J., Implementing the Theory of Sum Frequency Generation Vibrational Spectroscopy: A Tutorial Review. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews* **2005**, *40*, 103-145.

41. Richmond, G. L., Molecular Bonding and Interactions at Aqueous Surfaces as Probed by Vibrational Sum Frequency Spectroscopy *Chem Rev* **2002**, *102*, 2693-2724.
42. Zhuang, X.; Miranda, P. B.; Kim, D.; Shen, Y. R., Mapping Molecular Orientation and Conformation at Interfaces by Surface Nonlinear Optics. *Phys. Rev. B* **1999**, *59*, 12632-12640.
43. Sung, J.; Park, K.; Kim, D., Surfaces of Alcohol–Water Mixtures Studied by Sum-Frequency Generation Vibrational Spectroscopy. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2005**, *109*, 18507-18514.
44. Mileva, E., Impact of Adsorption Layers on Thin Liquid Films. *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science* **2010**, *15*, 315-323.
45. D. Exerova; Kruglyakov, P. M., *Foam and Foam Films: Theory, Experiment, Application*; NY: Marcel Dekker: New York, 1997.
46. Sheludko, A., Thin Liquid Films. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **1967**, *1*, 391-464.
47. Cosima, S.; Regine von, K., Disjoining Pressure in Thin Liquid Foam and Emulsion Films—New Concepts and Perspectives. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **2003**, *15*, R1197.
48. Yaminsky, V. V.; Ohnishi, S.; Vogler, E. A.; Horn, R. G., Stability of Aqueous Films between Bubble: Part 1: The Effect of Speed on Bubble Coalescence in Purified Water and Simple Electrolyte Solutions. *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 8061-8074.
49. Derjaguin, B.; Obuchov, E., *Kolloidn Zh* **1935**, *1*, 385.
50. Deryaguin, B. V., *Theory of the Stability of Colloids and Thin Films*, 1989.
51. Derjaguin, B.; Landau, L., Theory of the Stability of Strongly Charged Lyophobic Sols and of the Adhesion of Strongly Charged Particles in Solutions of Electrolytes. *Progress in Surface Science* **1993**, *43*, 30-59.
52. Verwey, E. J. W., *Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, 1948.
53. Wang, L., Drainage and Rupture of Thin Foam Films in the Presence of Ionic and Non-Ionic Surfactants. *International Journal of Mineral Processing* **2012**, *102–103*, 58-68.
54. Kralchevsky, P. A.; Danov, K. D.; Basheva, E. S., Hydration Force Due to the Reduced Screening of the Electrostatic Repulsion in Few-Nanometer-Thick Films. *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science* **2011**, *16*, 517-524.
55. J. K. Angarska; B. S. Dimitrova; K. D. Danov; P. A. Kralchevsky; K. P. Ananthapadmanabhan; Lips, A., Detection of the Hydrophobic Surface Forces in Foam Films by Measurements of the Critical Thickness of the Film Rupture. *Langmuir* **2004**, *20*, 1799-1806.
56. Danov, K. D.; Ivanov, I. B.; Ananthapadmanabhan, K. P.; Lips, A., Disjoining Pressure of Thin Films Stabilized by Nonionic Surfactants. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **2006**, *128–130*, 185-215.
57. Israelachvili, J. N., *Intermolecular and Surface Forces*, 2nd ed.; Academic Press: London, 1991.
58. N. V. Churaev; B. V. Derjaguin; Muller, V. M., *Surface Forces*; Springer, 1987.
59. Radoëv, B. P.; Dimitrov, D. S.; Ivanov, I. B., Hydrodynamics of Thin Liquid Films Effect of the Surfactant on the Rate of Thinning. *Colloid and Polymer Science* **1974**, *252*, 50-55.
60. Scheludko, A., Thin Liquid Films. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **1967**, *1*, 391-464.
61. Birdi, K. S., *Handbook of Surface and Colloid Chemistry* CRC Press: Pittsburgh, 2008.
62. Lucassen, J.; Van Den Tempel, M., Dynamic Measurements of Dilational Properties of a Liquid Interface. *Chemical Engineering Science* **1972**, *27*, 1283-1291.
63. Karakashev, S. I.; Manev, E. D., Hydrodynamics of Thin Liquid Films: Retrospective and Perspectives. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **2015**, *222*, 398-412.
64. Wells, P. V., Thickness of Stratified Films. *Ann. Phys.* **1921**, *16*, 69-110.
65. Perrin, J., The Stratification of Liquid Films. *Ann. Phys.* **1918**, *10*, 160.
66. Scheludko, A., Neues in Der Untersuchung Dünner Schichten. *Pure Appl. Chem.* **1965**, *10*, 323-336.
67. Nguyen, A. V.; Schulze, H. J., *Colloidal Science of Floatation*; Marcel Dekker: New York, 2004.
68. Tan, S. N.; Pugh, R. J.; Fornasiero, D.; Sedev, R.; Ralston, J., Foaming of Polypropylene Glycols and Glycol/Mibc Mixtures. *Minerals Engineering* **2005**, *18*, 179-188.

69. Nguyen, K. T.; Nguyen, A. V., In Situ Investigation of Halide Co-Ion Effects on Sds Adsorption at Air-Water Interfaces. *Soft Matter* **2014**, *10*, 6556-6563.
70. Hey, M. J.; Kippax, P. G., Surface Tensions of Mixed Aqueous Solutions of Tert-Butanol and N-Pentanol. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2005**, *262*, 198-203.
71. Comley, B. A.; Harris, P. J.; Bradshaw, D. J.; Harris, M. C., Frother Characterisation Using Dynamic Surface Tension Measurements. *Int J Miner Process* **2002**, *64*, 81-100.
72. Khoshdast, H.; Abbasi, H.; Sam, A.; Noghabi, K. A., Frothability and Surface Behavior of a Rhamnolipid Biosurfactant Produced by *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* Ma01. *Biochem Eng J* **2012**, *60*, 127-134.
73. Nguyen, C. V.; Phan, C. M.; Ang, H. M.; Nakahara, H.; Shibata, O.; Moroi, Y., Surface Potential of 1-Hexanol Solution: Comparison with Methyl Isobutyl Carbinol. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2013**, *117*, 7615-7620.
74. Cui, X.; Mao, S.; Liu, M.; Yuan, H.; Du, Y., Mechanism of Surfactant Micelle Formation. *Langmuir* **2008**, *24*, 10771-10775.
75. Qu, X.; Wang, L.; Karakashev, S. I.; Nguyen, A. V., Anomalous Thickness Variation of the Foam Films Stabilized by Weak Non-Ionic Surfactants. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2009**, *337*, 538-547.
76. Ward, A. F. H.; Tordai, L., Time-Dependence of Boundary Tensions of Solutions I. The Role of Diffusion in Time-Effects. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1946**, *14*, 453-461.
77. Fainerman, V. B.; Makievski, A. V.; Miller, R., The Analysis of Dynamic Surface Tension of Sodium Alkyl Sulphate Solutions, Based on Asymptotic Equations of Adsorption Kinetic Theory. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **1994**, *87*, 61-75.
78. Sung, W.; Kim, D.; Shen, Y. R., Sum-Frequency Vibrational Spectroscopic Studies of Langmuir Monolayers. *Current Applied Physics* **2013**, *13*, 619-632.
79. Tuinier, R.; Bisperink, C. G. J.; van den Berg, C.; Prins, A., Transient Foaming Behavior of Aqueous Alcohol Solutions as Related to Their Dilational Surface Properties. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **1996**, *179*, 327-334.
80. Saavedra, O. A.; Gracia Fadrique, J., Langmuir Isotherm Explains Maximum Foamability. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2016**, *497*, 41-44.
81. Kovalchuk, V. I.; Miller, R.; Fainerman, V. B.; Loglio, G., Dilational Rheology of Adsorbed Surfactant Layers—Role of the Intrinsic Two-Dimensional Compressibility. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **2005**, *114–115*, 303-312.
82. Ling Hao; Leaist, D. G., Binary Mutual Diffusion Coefficients of Aqueous Alcohols: Methanol to 1-Heptanol. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **1996**, *41*, 210-213.
83. Nelson, P., *Biological Physics. Energy, Information, Life*; WH Freeman and Company: New York, 2008.
84. Abrankó-Rideg, N.; Darvas, M.; Horvai, G.; Jedlovszky, P., Immersion Depth of Surfactants at the Free Water Surface: A Computer Simulation and Itim Analysis Study. *J Phys Chem B* **2013**, *117*, 8733-8746.